

Cultivating FAIR principles for multi-hazard assessment

Bonatis P.¹, Anagnostou V.¹, Karakostas V.¹, Kourouklas C.¹, Papadimitriou E.¹, Adamaki A.², Andriopoulou-Mounteanou S-A.³, Bathrellos G.D.³, Bitharis S.¹, Foumelis M.¹, Karolos I-A.¹, Kaviris G.⁴, Papageorgiou E.¹, Pikridas C.¹, Sakkas V.¹, Skilodimou H.D.³, Spingos I.⁴, Zymvragakis A.⁴

(1) Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece, mponatis@geo.auth.gr (2) Lund University, Lund, Sweden (3) University of Patras, Rio, Greece (4) National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece

Research Highlights

- HOMEROS stands for “Harmonising Observations from Multi-hazard Environments in Research for Open Science”.
- The project aims to deliver FAIR-compliant tools and datasets to enhance disaster preparedness and resilience in high-risk regions through transparent and collaborative research.

Introduction

In today’s interconnected world, communities face a diverse range of hazards, including natural disasters like earthquakes, floods, and landslides, as well as human-induced events. To address these challenges, the HOMEROS project aims to strengthen multi-hazard assessment methodologies in seismology, geodesy, and geology (Figure 1). Leveraging technical solutions suited to the big data era, HOMEROS represents a significant advancement in standardizing research processes, promoting collaboration, and enhancing understanding and prediction capabilities for natural hazards through Open Science practices. By adhering to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), HOMEROS ensures that its research outputs are transparent, reproducible, and universally accessible, maximizing their value for the scientific community and stakeholders. Focusing on high-risk areas in Greece with significant seismic activity, strong earthquakes, floods, and landslides, HOMEROS will compile earthquake catalogues and assess ground deformation products to provide a comprehensive evaluation of seismic hazards. Additionally, it will enhance the understanding of flood and landslide risks, vital for effective mitigation strategies.

Figure 1. Official logo of the HOMEROS project, highlighting its multi-hazard focus

Objectives

The HOMEROS project addresses the critical need for robust and standardized multi-hazard assessment methodologies in a rapidly evolving risk landscape. By leveraging the power of Open Science and interdisciplinary collaboration, the project aims to advance scientific knowledge, foster data-driven decision-making, and enhance community resilience. Its objectives focus on three key pillars:

- Integration with Open Science environments: HOMEROS aims to utilize platforms such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Environmental Research Infrastructure (ENMRI) Hub (Adamaki & Vermeulen, 2023) to create accessible ecosystems for data sharing. This builds on prior integration efforts in ENMRI projects and promotes FAIR principles to ensure the usability and reproducibility of research outputs.
- Enhancing multi-hazard assessment: The project seeks to develop methodologies for integrating diverse datasets, including seismic, geodetic, and geological data. It will advance the understanding of earthquakes, floods, and landslides through the creation of detailed models, maps, and inventories.
- Fostering collaboration and communication: HOMEROS aspires to strengthen partnerships among research institutions, infrastructures, and projects. Results will be shared through Open Access publications, workshops, and training resources.

Multi-hazard environments - Pilot areas

The HOMEROS project focuses on two high-risk pilot areas in Greece, the central Ionian Islands and the western Gulf of Corinth (Figure 2), which represent diverse and complex multi-hazard environments. These regions have been selected due to their significant seismic activity and susceptibility to other natural hazards, such as floods and landslides. By studying these areas, HOMEROS aims to develop and demonstrate innovative methodologies for multi-hazard assessment.

Figure 2. Map of the pilot areas encompassing the central Ionian Islands and western Corinth gulf. Different symbols denote the epicenters of all known earthquakes in the study area with magnitudes $M > 4.0$ as shown in the upper right inset. The central inset shows the territory of Greece with the study area enclosed in the red polygon. Hexagons illustrate the positions of the seismological stations providing online access to their recordings. Yellow triangles depict the installation sites of GNSS stations in operation, whereas the olive triangles the positions where additional GNSS stations are planned to be installed in the framework of the project, collocated with already existing and operated seismological stations.

The central Ionian Islands, along with the western Gulf of Corinth, accommodate the highest seismicity in the eastern Mediterranean, exhibiting high deformation rates (Pikridas et al., 2016; Bitharis et al., 2024) and frequent occurrences of strong earthquakes (e.g., Karakostas et al., 2015; Sakkas et al., 2022). The compilation of earthquake catalogues (e.g. from the Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre - EMSC, the European Plate Observing System - EPOS providers as the ORFEUS infrastructure, the database of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki - AUTH seismological center, and others), comprising historical, instrumental, and recent events, along with focal mechanism and stress field data, represent a significant contribution to the understanding of seismic hazard. Earthquakes are among the most impactful geohazards in Greece given that more than 50% of seismic energy in Europe is released in the country. A reliable seismic hazard model can contribute to seismic risk mitigation. To that end, Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) and Peak Ground Velocity (PGV) together with a site-specific analysis (Uniform Hazard Spectra - UHS and hazard curves) in the most populated towns can provide a holistic evaluation of seismic hazard (e.g., Kaviris et al., 2022; 2024). Besides strong earthquakes, the aforementioned areas along with parts of the northern Peloponnese have experienced severe floods and landslides that resulted in loss of life and substantial loss of property, along with extensive damage to the natural and built environment and key infrastructure (Bathrellos et al., 2017; Skilodimou et al., 2018). Maps displaying the spatial distribution of flood and landslide hazards are invaluable at identifying areas at risk (Skilodimou et al., 2019; Bathrellos et al., 2024). The project will enhance the understanding of the spatial distribution of historical and recently recorded floods, along with the identification of flood – prone areas, which constitute critical input information on effective flood-risk mitigation. Regarding landslides, they are mostly observed in the mountainous part of the Gulf of Corinth, the Ionian Islands, and parts of western Peloponnese, where serious damage has been repeatedly caused to sections of urban areas and the road network. Landslide hazard assessment maps are important tools for prediction and mitigation of natural disasters. In this context, the project will work on an inventory map that includes recorded landslide events, crucial for understanding the landslide hazard.

Data and Methods

Comprehensive multi-hazard assessment requires diverse data sources and advanced methodologies to address the complexity of natural hazards. HOMEROS will integrate high-quality datasets from seismology, geodesy, and geological monitoring to provide robust and reproducible insights. Seismic data from regional networks form the basis for compiling earthquake catalogues, analyzing focal mechanisms, and studying ground deformation, all of which are critical inputs for seismic hazard assessment. Geodetic observations, including GNSS and InSAR, enhance the understanding of tectonic deformation (Bonatis et al., 2024) and enable the integration of precise ground deformation monitoring with broader hazard assessments. Flood and landslide hazards can be assessed using historical records and remote sensing data. Spatial analyses and advanced techniques, such as InSAR, help to identify flood and landslide prone areas (Aslan et al., 2020). These methods are complemented by the development of inventories that catalog historical events. A key component of the project is the harmonization of data and the application of Open Science principles to ensure all research outputs are transparent, reproducible, and widely accessible. Collaborative platforms and tools will be utilized to integrate datasets from diverse sources, fostering interdisciplinary research and promoting knowledge sharing. Reproducible workflows will enable the seamless combination of datasets and methodologies to deliver actionable insights into natural hazards.

Exploitable results

The HOMEROS project aims to deliver a range of results that will significantly advance multi-hazard assessment and enhance disaster resilience (Table 1). A primary output will be open-access datasets, including earthquake catalogues, ground deformation products, flood hazard maps, and landslide inventories. These datasets will adhere to FAIR principles and will be shared through platforms such as EPOS ERIC, ENVRI repositories, and other open repositories (e.g., GitHub, Zenodo). These data products will provide valuable resources for advancing research and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration.

Another key outcome is the development of transparent and reproducible research workflows documented through tools like Jupyter Notebooks. These workflows will demonstrate the integration of diverse datasets and methodologies, enabling researchers to replicate and adapt the processes for similar studies. This documentation will serve as a best-practice guide for future multi-disciplinary research projects.

Table 1. Summary of the key outcomes of HOMEROS

Output	Description	Impact
Open-access datasets	Comprehensive datasets including earthquake catalogues, ground deformation products (GNSS and InSAR), flood hazard maps, and landslide inventories.	Enabling improved hazard modeling, interdisciplinary research, and data-driven policy-making.
Scientific publications	Peer-reviewed articles published in Open Access journals, showcasing HOMEROS methodologies and findings.	Advancing scientific knowledge.
Training modules	Educational resources designed to teach Open Science principles, data sharing practices, and the utilization of research tools like Jupyter Notebooks and ENVRI/EOSC services.	Capacity building among researchers, students, and professionals, fostering widespread adoption of Open Science practices.
Integration demonstrators	Showcase of pathways to integrate data pipelines from diverse sources, including ENVRI and EOSC infrastructures, to highlight interoperability and scalability.	Improved data interoperability.
Policy recommendations support tools	Practical outputs such as hazard maps and risk models suited for policymakers and disaster management stakeholders.	Enhancing disaster preparedness and resilience.

Conclusions

HOMEROS represents a vital step forward in addressing the growing complexity of multi-hazard environments. By harmonizing data from diverse scientific domains and adhering to Open Science principles, the project tackles key challenges in making hazard assessment both comprehensive and accessible. It lays the foundation for more integrated and scalable approaches to understand natural hazards, from earthquakes to floods and landslides, in high-risk regions. The emphasis on FAIR principles ensures that HOMEROS outputs not only benefit current research but also provide a robust framework for future innovations in hazard modeling. The project's focus on high-risk areas, such as the Ionian Islands and the Gulf of Corinth, will demonstrate its applicability, while offering scalable solutions that can be adapted to other geohazardous regions worldwide. Lastly, the outputs including open-access data, scientific publications, and training modules, will serve as valuable resources for academia, policy-making, and disaster management, fostering a safer and more resilient society.

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